

**TRAINING OF PERSONNEL, WORKING WITH THEM, PUTTING
THEM IN PLACE, IMPROVING THEIR SKILLS AND FORMING THE
PERSONNEL RESERVE .**

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Annotation: In the article, the selection and placement of personnel in the educational system of the goals of sustainable development, as well as some existing problems in this field, were studied and their specific features were analyzed.

Key words: Leader and pedagogic personnel, continuing education, public education system, higher education, personnel planning, personnel needs, professional development.

Improving the selection and placement of teaching staff is an important condition for successfully solving the tasks facing any country and strengthening education. At the same time, the problem of forming a team of highly qualified teaching staff in any school is one of the most complex problems of the public education system. Selection of pedagogic personnel, development of scientific criteria for evaluation of their activity, analysis of personnel needs, placement of pedagogic personnel are necessary to solve the issues of formation of effective technologies. In order to solve the priority tasks in working with pedagogic staff, it is necessary to study the world experience of improving the implementation of personnel policy in our country, working with personnel, creating a new system of training. The studies show that the scientific foundations of working with personnel have not been sufficiently studied in our country, new approaches to the formation of personnel, methods and means of studying the personality have not been scientifically fundamentally researched, and, at the same time, the evaluation and promotion of personnel activities scientific bases are not systematized. Including, in the system of public education, these issues lead to the need for additional theoretical research in the areas of selection, placement and support of

leaders, specialists and pedagogues, as well as in the search for advanced technologies for working with management and pedagogical personnel. brings

The analysis of scientific sources related to this topic shows that the category of "personnel" is understood in direct connection with such concepts as "labor force", "human capital", "labor resources", "personnel", "qualified specialist", "human factor". Such an approach can be accepted as reasonable in many respects. But, in our opinion, in the process of training highly educated personnel and qualified specialists, the cognitive ability of a person, that is, as it was mentioned above, his perception of surrounding things, reality, events and information, making the right decision based on pre-imagining and analyzing them, putting it into practice opportunities, talent and experience should be taken into account. In addition, the characteristics of trusting, loving and patient approach to the personnel while performing their profession also play a special role.

In our opinion, from an economic point of view, labor resources are an economic category that covers the processes of production, on the one hand, and the formation, distribution and use of personnel potential, on the other. Based on this, we can say that the concept of personnel potential is directly related to the category of "labor resources" and is one of its structural elements. The concept of "personnel" is a phrase that is relatively quick and often used in most cases, and it mainly describes the categories of managers and qualified specialists who work directly in enterprises, companies and industries that are close in terms of specialization . For example, according to the definition of the economist R. Kolosova, "personnel" is a group of people who have special professional qualifications based on the specific aspects of the industry and enterprises and who are constantly working in this industry and are a part of labor resources.

Regarding the issue of qualified personnel related to agriculture, S. Kensuken emphasizes that "the main source of production of agricultural enterprises is labor resources, the quality and efficiency of which are fully dependent on business results and financial stability. According to him, "the development of agricultural enterprises

is very sensitive to the skills, knowledge, motivation, ability to solve social and economic problems of employees. In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, it is defined as "personnel is a servant, worker and employee of an enterprise, institution with special training", and in the Wikipedia encyclopedia, "personnel is qualified employees of enterprises, institutions, firms, joint-stock companies, banks, trade unions and public organizations." main content" is described in the content.

Economists have expressed many opinions and comments about the meaning and essence of the concept of personnel, which is specific to agriculture. Summarizing them in the process of research, in our opinion, it will be possible to understand them from two points of view, that is, in a broad and narrow sense. The concept of personnel in a broad sense represents workers, farmers, entrepreneurs, leaders and specialists, while the concept of personnel in a narrow sense is understood as the skilled (higher and secondary educated) part of those engaged in physical and mental labor.

In conclusion, based on the above points, it is correct to understand the leaders and experts who have undergone special professional training for a certain period of time (short and long) by the term "personnel". According to the content of labor activity and functional tasks, personnel are divided into 4 levels from a classical point of view: managerial personnel, specialist personnel, service personnel, and working personnel. Therefore, the general aspect of the concept of personnel reflects their connection with the fact that they have a certain specialty and the necessary knowledge and skills, and embodying a certain potential, they form a group of workers and specialists who have personal, business and professional training.

The development of the system of training qualified personnel for agriculture in our country was carried out in three stages.

According to him, the first stage includes the years 1991-2005 and it can be called the stage of creating the organizational and legal basis of this system. At this stage, there are agricultural technical schools, vocational colleges, higher education institutions, research institutes, and training centers as institutions for training qualified

personnel, which are distinguished by differences in the form of education, admission procedure, and duration of education.

In recent years, the level of the graduates of higher education institutions, which is below the expected standards, is also a cause for concern. Studies show that the majority of graduates do not have the knowledge that corresponds to the profile of their activity. In the system of public education, there is a shortage of highly qualified specialists to fully organize the management and educational processes of educational institutions. This problem cannot be solved without a scientifically based concept of personnel policy. In addition, the selection and placement of leaders, experts and pedagogues in educational systems, as in all fields, should be based on scientific principles. It is known that the issue of working with personnel includes personnel planning, selection, improvement of their qualifications, evaluation and promotion of personnel activities, their social control and protection. The basis of this work should be personnel planning - the process of providing the institution with qualified personnel accepted for the right positions at the right time . The task of personnel planning is to translate the goals and plans of the institution into specific needs for qualified personnel. Any organization and institution must use personnel planning when setting strategic goals. Therefore, some of them conduct serious research in this field, while others approach the issue superficially. In any case, the success of any organization and institution depends on the presence of necessary qualified employees in the relevant positions. The goals and strategies of organizations and institutions become important only when specialists are engaged in achieving these goals. A superficial approach to this issue, working with unqualified or careless personnel can lead to serious problems. Filling vacant positions with the help of high-performance personnel planning reduces employee turnover and creates an opportunity to assess the capabilities of specialists within the institution. Personnel planning is the determination of the general personnel needs of the institution. This is the calculation of the required number of employees based on their number, qualifications, time, employment and placement in accordance with the development goals of the institution. The calculation is based on the

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Today, determining the need for personnel in the field of education is one of the most problematic aspects of personnel planning. The reason for this is the lack of scientific criteria and scientifically based recommendations for determining the number of employees. True, today there are initiatives in this field, but most of them do not have a logical conclusion. Therefore, Decree No. PF6108 of the President of the

Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 6, 2020 "On measures for the development of education and science in the period of new development of Uzbekistan " [4, 1] and Resolution PQ-4884 "On additional measures to further improve the education system" [5, 1] and On the basis of Decision No. PQ-4963 of January 25, 2021 "On measures to support scientific research activities in the field of public education and to introduce a continuous professional development system" [6, 1] Scientific research work is being conducted to study the basics of the problems listed above.

LIST OF REFERENCES USED

1. Decree No. PF-5538 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 5, 2018 "On additional measures to improve the management system of public education".

2. Resolution PQ-3931 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 5, 2018 "On measures to introduce new management principles into the public education system".

3. Decree No. PF-4947 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 "On the Action Strategy for Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan".

4. Decree No. PF-6108 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 6, 2020 "On measures to develop the fields of education and science in the new development period of Uzbekistan".

5. Decision PQ-4884 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 6, 2020 "On additional measures to further improve the education system".

6. Decision No. PQ-4963 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 25, 2021 "On measures to support scientific research activities in the field of public education and to introduce a continuous professional development system."